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Abstract:

Over the past two years SSHOC was able to participate and manage an intense inter-cluster exchange which produced several concrete outputs and set the bases for a permanent cooperation between ESFRI science clusters in the bigger framework of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This deliverable reports on the results of these cooperation activities.

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Executive Summary

SSHOC thematic cluster project (2019-2022) has built a strong and recognisable brand around a consortium of 5 ERICs and ESFRI Landmarks, 1 ESFRI project and onboarded Social Science and Humanities (SSH) data communities, 5 of them obtaining the status of ESFRI projects in the latest editions of ESFRI Roadmaps thus actively breaking down the silos through the sharing of knowledge, tools, and services with significant potential for further capacity-building as an important building block for EOSC.

SSHOC didn't only facilitate further collaboration within the SSH community regarding alignment of data, services, and interoperability solutions, and sharing of (thematic) services in EOSC. It reached out to other domains and researchers via peer projects funded by the European Commission (EC) in the framework of the INFRAEOSC-04 call aiming to link ESFRI landmarks and projects, as well as other ERICs to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). A series of regular consultations, joint initiatives, outputs, and presentations, described in this report, led the five clusters to link together and develop a common ground for collaboration beyond duration of projects.

Deliverable 8.6 is the final report on the cooperation activities of the SSHOC project with other science clusters:

- ENVRI-FAIR¹ for environmental research,
- PaNOSC² for multidisciplinary scientific analysis,
- ESCAPE³ for astronomy and particle physics,
- EOSC-Life⁴ for life sciences.

The activities described below are result of several streams of efforts: task 8.4 of the SSHOC project involving several project bodies and partners, as well as Coordinator's direct alignment with other cluster projects.

¹ ENVRI-FAIR website: <https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/> (accessed April 2022)

² PANOSC website: <https://www.panosc.eu> (accessed April 2022)

³ ESCAPE website: <https://projectescape.eu> (accessed April 2022)

⁴ EOSC Life website: <https://www.eosc-life.eu> (accessed April 2022)

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CoP	Community of Practice
ESCAPE	The European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle Physics ESFRI Research Infrastructures (Cluster project)
ENVRI-FAIR	Environmental RIs building FAIR services for research, innovation, and society (Cluster project)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-Life	Cluster project for Life Science RIs to create an open, collaborative digital space for life science in the EOSC
ESFRI	European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructures
HE	Horizon Europe funding programme
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
PANOSC	The Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud (Cluster project)
RI	Research Infrastructure
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud

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1. Introduction

This deliverable describes relationship developed throughout the SSHOC project with other EOSC science clusters at different levels and the related activities with the aim to share best practices and to facilitate collaboration among the five clusters to optimise efforts related to common challenges. It is propaedeutic to the final comprehensive report to be delivered at Month 40 (D8.6: Report on inter-cluster cooperation activities).

The deliverable includes the description of cluster collaboration at different levels, addressing issues ranging from governance and sustainability to technical, competence building, or communication and including all the relevant stakeholders involved in different aspects and development of the ESFRI landscape and its aligned contribution to EOSC environment. The cooperation among the clusters aimed at sharing experiences and jointly addressing common topics such as: data interoperability, policy development, tools, and services, EOSC integration, training, innovation – and comparing approaches, best practices, and building future strategies.

To achieve the objective of the task 8.4, coordination of input was organised with support from WP2 to capture different alignment activities among cluster projects, led by the Coordinator of SSHOC, and to share information on collaborative actions regarding:

- streamlining interaction between cluster projects,
- linking the outputs of separate ESFRI research infrastructures and projects to the actions of cluster projects,
- comparing technical aspects e.g., best practices, use cases, success stories between cluster projects
- showcasing the use-cases and cross-cluster collaboration.

Details of regular clusters' alignment and its outcomes are detailed below.

2. Coordination and alignment of efforts

The SSHOC consortium has proven that research infrastructures from the SSH domain can jointly provide a valuable service offer, with use cases within the social sciences and humanities and with potential for impact in other domains.

Since 2019, 5 cluster projects coordinators engaged in more than 70 regular bi-weekly meetings chaired by the SSHOC Coordinator. However, alignment started back in 2018 while preparing 5 proposals for the INFRAEOSC-04 call. After projects were granted funding and after initial consolidation of partnerships and work, alignment calls started again, in a more coordinated manner, led by the SSHOC project coordination team. However, not only coordinators were aligning their strategic directions; training, technical and communication teams were having their own coordination meetings and activities throughout the duration of the SSHOC project.

2.1 Joint outputs

The coordinators of the five INFRA EOSC-04 cluster projects have been meeting regularly over the past few years. Their strategic alignment has resulted in a number of tangible outputs: two position papers on ESFRI clusters: Position paper on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC (2020), and ESFRI Science Clusters Position Statement on Expectations and Long-Term Commitment in Open Science (2021). The latter was jointly presented to the wider community in the stakeholder engagement event “ESFRI Science Clusters' Long-Term Commitments to Open Science”⁵ held on 11th June 2021.

The last joint statement was the response to the EOSC Association’s consultation on the new HE RI work programme for funding period 2023-2024, as well as some other initiatives.

Other outputs and joint initiatives aiming at alignment of efforts in different areas have been ongoing since 2019:

- Two cross-cluster events where representatives of the five cluster projects discussed commonalities and collaboration regarding research data management solutions, thematic data services, connecting to end-user communities, and governance:
 - “Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services”⁶ held on 21 October 2019 at the 14th RDA Plenary meeting, and

⁵ ESFRI Science Clusters' long term commitments to open science online workshop on SSHOC website:

<https://sshopencloud.eu/events/esfri-science-clusters-long-term-commitments-open-science> (accessed April 2022)

⁶ EOSC, ESFRI Cluster Projects, RDA: Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/eosc-esfri-cluster-projects-rda%C2%A0connecting-commonalities-and-collaborative-solutions-community> (accessed April 2022)

- “The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons”⁷ held on 19 April 2021 at the 17th RDA Plenary meeting.
- Realising EOSC⁸ conference as a joint activity of SSHOC, FREYA, and EOSC-Hub projects promoted and supported the integration of different stakeholder communities in the realisation of EOSC, covering cross-cluster topics such as sustainability, citizen science, onboarding of tools and services, and thematic marketplaces. The conference included an exposition of 33 EOSC projects.
- Participation in RDA working and interest groups.
- Participation in metadata catalogue integration work initiated by FAIRsFAIR⁹ project.
- SSHOC Marketplace/WP7 efforts in collaboration with other cluster cataloguing initiatives.
- Training efforts/WP6 alignment across clusters. To this end, interaction has been established between the SSH Training Community¹⁰ and the OpenAIRE¹¹ CoP for training coordinators¹². The SSH Trainers Directory¹³ offers visibility of the trainers not only to the SSH community, but also to other domains.

A more in-depth discussion on technical details built on the invested efforts in developing, adopting, and sharing experience and solutions across RIs belonging to different clusters.

Among other more intangible outputs (mutual support, shared experiences, and know-how), it resulted in the complete overview of tools and services produced by SSHOC project with clear indications for future maintenance and further development, hence, sustainability and exploitation mapping.

Finally, within WP2, a mapping exercise had been undertaken and was continuously updated to track interactions and overlaps among activities of the cluster projects.

More detailed overview of results of cross-cluster coordination is offered below.

⁷ The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons Report announcement: <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/esfri-clusters-rda-house-commons-report-out-now> (accessed April 2022)

⁸ Realising the European Open Cloud conference page: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud> (accessed April 2022)

⁹ FairSFair project page: <https://www.fairsfair.eu> (accessed April 2022)

¹⁰ SSH Training Community page: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/ssh-training-community> (accessed April 2022)

¹¹ OpenAire Page: <https://www.openaire.eu> (accessed April 2022)

¹² OpenAire Community of practice page: <https://www.openaire.eu/cop-training> (accessed April 2022)

¹³ SSHOC Trainers Directory: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/trainers-directory> (accessed April 2022)

2.1.1 Position papers and joint statements

The regular consultations among the cluster coordinators led to publication of two joint position papers representing the strategic alignment between the science clusters.

The first publication, **“ESFRI cluster projects - Position paper on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC”**¹⁴ was published in December 2019. The need to leverage domain expertise and better drive the innovation which research communities require was stated in these position papers reflecting views and expectations about EOSC and the contributions of ESFRI clusters to the European data infrastructure. As stakeholders of EOSC, cluster projects were invited to contribute to its development and implementation process. These position papers were the tools for the projects to contribute directly to development of EOSC and identify ways for synergies in driving innovations within EOSC towards the research community’s needs.

The papers revolved around following topics:

- Expectations of the research community.
- The added value of EOSC to the existing research infrastructure.
- Issues to be addressed by the EOSC Executive board.
- Commitments to EOSC.
- A summary of the common viewpoints of the projects’ recommendations was the following:
- A clear and concise communication of the concept of EOSC is required.
- A common standard for FAIR data needs to be defined to create a common understanding across communities.
- A research community-centred bottom-up approach needs to be prioritised.
- EOSC needs to aspire to offer a continuous, trusted working environment and networking opportunities to the research community.
- EOSC needs to provide a long-term open data archive with high performance storage and computing services, to enable sustainable use of data beyond the life span of individual data infrastructures.
- The EOSC infrastructure needs to provide cross-Europe AAI, high performance storage, computing, archiving, simulation, and analysis services, to build a Minimum Viable Ecosystem. Encouraged participation will make the idea of EOSC adoptable by the research community.
- Beyond the provision of open data, EOSC needs to aspire to create a virtual research space for open science, where scientists can create content and collaborate.
- Collaborate with publishers to make open data a publication.
- EOSC is required to show a cost-benefit analysis to participating research communities.
- A documentation of guidelines on how to join and use EOSC services is needed.

¹⁴ Gotz, Andy, Petzold, Andreas, Asmi, Ari, Blomberg, Niklas, Lamanna, Giovanni, & Dekker, Ron. (2020). ESFRI cluster projects - Position papers on expectations and planned contributions to the EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3675081>

- The business model of the Federating Core must be positioned at the national level, so that governments have the interest to encourage open science and define the national policies that can support it.

The second position paper, “**ESFRI Science Clusters Position Statement on Expectations and Long-Term Commitment in Open Science**”¹⁵ was published in June 2021, contributing to explain the need to support a longer-term role of the five Science Clusters to provide content to the EOSC, to enhance researchers’ involvement in Open Science and to suggest potential cooperative pathways in the Horizon-Europe framework and along with the EOSC Association roadmap.

The main impacts of the Science Clusters’ work programme concern:

- the improved access of researchers to data, tools, and resources, leading to new insights and innovation for data-driven science both within and beyond the context of the domains in which the clusters are rooted.
- the creation of a cross-border open innovation environment for FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data management for economies of scale, to develop synergies and raise the efficiency and productivity of researchers through open-science standards and thematic services.
- the enhanced co-developments to foster the cross-domain interoperability central to the EOSC goal.

The second position statement document was written based on the various interactions between the science clusters and the European Commission, the EOSC Association, the governing bodies of the ESFRI RI partners, and on constant cooperative work between the management boards of the five science cluster projects in the past years. This paper was jointly presented to the wider community in the stakeholder engagement event “ESFRI Science Clusters’ Long-Term Commitments to Open Science”¹⁶ on 21 June 2021.

In September 2021, 5 clusters wrote a joint statement in response to the EOSC Association’s consultation on the new Horizon Europe Research Infrastructure Work Programme for funding period 2023-2024. Titled “**Fostering Open Science with Science Clusters of ESFRI research infrastructures through both community-based and interdisciplinary projects and common actions**” the statement focused on their expectations from EOSC:

- Implementation of EOSC (addressing the scientific needs for additional services, interoperability, and alignment)

¹⁵ Giovanni Lamanna, Ian Bird, Andreas Petzold, Ari Asmi, Magdalena Brus, Niklas Blomberg, Michael Räß, Rudolf Dimper, Andrew Gotz, & Ron Dekker. (2021). ESFRI Science Clusters Position Statement on Expectations and Long-Term Commitment in Open Science (1.02). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4892245>

¹⁶ ESFRI Science Clusters’ Long Term Commitments to Open Science workshop page: <https://eosc-portal.eu/events/esfri-science-clusters-long-term-commitments-open-science> (accessed April 2022)

- Metadata and Data Quality (fostering transversal actions towards FAIR stewardship and continued innovation of scientific software)
- Widening and Outreach (targeting open innovation environment for research data, knowledge and services with engaged stakeholders and organisations)
- Sustaining EOSC (providing a sustainable model for science communities to contribute to the EOSC).

Clusters urged EOSC Association to address the stewardship of digital objects from research infrastructures and build on previous and current developments of the ESFRI Science Clusters, engaging with new communities (even globally), and new projects that have been included in the recently updated ESFRI roadmap¹⁷, to accelerate the uptake of these best practices more broadly. According to clusters, next HE actions should include the integration of ESFRI science clusters' major thematic services as part of EOSC for domain-specific data management as well as the final implementation and operation of open-science virtual research environments for depositing, curating, and analysing data.

In addition, all cluster were asked to produce so-called "Project briefs" in December 2021, to support the upcoming HE programme and policy activities in the period of 2023-2024. Project briefs asked to address internal developments regarding five broad areas of interest for the EC, with focus on main results achieved so far, expected developments by the end of the project, and recommendations and follow-up priorities linked to the further development of EOSC:

1. Integration with EOSC infrastructure
2. FAIR principles implementation and repositories
3. Technical, semantic, legal, and organisational interoperability
4. Stewardship of data
5. Cross-cluster collaboration

SSHOC project brief¹⁸ described its strong and recognisable brand built around a consortium of 6 well-established ESFRIs, 7 onboarded Social Science and Humanities (SSH) data communities, an SSH Open Marketplace testers' community and an SSH Training Community actively breaking down the silos through the sharing of knowledge, tools, and services with significant potential for further capacity-building as an important building block for EOSC.

Regarding further development of EOSC, and in the light of cross-cluster collaboration, SSHOC strongly recommended the active use of the unique positioning of the science clusters between the EOSC and domain research infrastructures for providing direct communication channels to end-users. Also, it urged

¹⁷ ESFRI Roadmap 2021 page: <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-roadmap-2021> (accessed April 2022)

¹⁸ Ron Dekker, Martina Drascic Capar, Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Vanja Komljenovic, Veronika Heider, Mari Kleemola, Elizabeth Lea Bishop, Mathilde Steinsvåg Hansen, Daan Broeder, Franciska de Jong, Maria Eskevitch, Darja Fišer, Emiliano Degl'Innocenti, Carmen Di Meo, Monica Monachini, Luca Pezzati, Jana Striova, Nicolas Larrousse, Laure Barbot, ... Holly Wright. (2021). SSHOC Project Brief To support the EC Programme and policy activities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5769762>

the EC to ensure continued collaboration between the science clusters thus enabling a creation of a landscape supporting a cross-disciplinary collaboration able to actively address complex societal challenges. Finally, it asked for the strong support in the development of the multidisciplinary research agendas requiring innovative methodologies for handling heterogeneous datasets rooted in multiple domains.

Finally, clusters aligned their positions in a few separate responses (i.e., **EOSC Association Board meets ongoing H2020 INFRAEOSC projects**, 8 April 2022 followed by a survey on key exploitable results, due on 1 May 2022).

2.1.2 Cross-cluster events

Two cross-cluster events were organised in the framework of RDA plenaries where representatives of the five cluster projects discussed commonalities and collaboration of cluster projects in community research data management solutions, thematic data services, connecting to end-user communities, and governance.

On 21 October 2019, during the Research Data Alliance 14th Plenary meeting held in Helsinki, SSHOC invited representatives from EOSC, the ESFRI cluster projects and the RDA Working and Interest Groups to discuss mutual commonalities and opportunities for collaboration. A cross-section of some 40 individuals attended the 4-hour co-located workshop titled **“EOSC. ESFRI cluster projects. RDA. Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services”**¹⁹. The outcomes of the event were summarised in the report²⁰.

One and a half years after the session in Helsinki, the five ESFRI cluster projects, the RDA community, and European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) representatives came together again to discuss the past, present and future of their collaboration during the journey of integrating thematic services into EOSC. **“The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons”**²¹ was organised by SSHOC and held as a co-located event on 19 April 2021 at the 17th RDA Plenary meeting.

The debate covered commonalities and collaboration in the ESFRI clusters regarding their contribution to the European Open Science Cloud on three pillar topics: thematic data services, connecting to end-user communities and governance. For each of these topics, the ESFRI cluster projects were asked for input from members of the international RDA community, the ESFRI community, EOSC ecosystem

¹⁹ EOSC, ESFRI Cluster Projects, RDA: Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services page: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/eosc-esfri-cluster-projects-rda%C2%A0connecting-commonalities-and-collaborative-solutions-community> (accessed April 2022)

²⁰ Ron Dekker, Daan Broeder, Franciska de Jong, Vasso Kalaitzi, Marieke Willems, Tracey Biller, Mingfang Wu, Marco Molinaro, Jonathan Clark, Ari Asmi, René van Horik, Mirjam van Daalen, & Ornella di Giacomo. (2019). EOSC. ESFRI Cluster Projects. RDA: Connecting commonalities and collaborative solutions for community research data services. Research Data Alliance Plenary 14 (RDA P14), Helsinki. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3581075>

²¹The ESFRI Clusters at RDA House of Commons Report announcement: <https://sshopencloud.eu/news/esfri-clusters-rda-house-commons-report-out-now> (accessed April 2022)

and data experts and domain researchers being the end-user community. Input from these stakeholder groups was collected through their involvement in the debating team and the active audience engagement.

“Realising the European Open Science Cloud - Towards a FAIR Research Data Landscape for the Social Sciences, Humanities and Beyond” virtual conference²² was organised by EOSC-Hub, FREYA and SSHOC projects. It was held from 16 to 19 November 2020. The conference gave a significant space to science clusters to discuss their approaches, best practices, and future common strategies in the plenary session titled “Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud”²³ successfully delivered on November 16, 2020.

The session was organised as part of internal SSHOC WP2-WP6 Stakeholder Series of events. It promoted and supported the integration of different stakeholder communities in the realisation of SSH part of EOSC, also covering cross-cluster topics such as sustainability, citizen science, onboarding of tools and services, and thematic marketplaces. It was evident that further steps need to be made to address aspects such as a convenience for users and providers, engagement, and participation of researchers, clarifying incentives for opening data, harmonisation of terminology for key entities, encouraging interoperability and sustainability of the systems, clarifying level of openness (embargoes, sensitive data, etc.), integration of services and data with knowledge and training.

Finally, **SSHOC final conference** was held on 6-7 April 2022 in Brussels as a hybrid event. With almost 300 people registered and out of it 91 joined the conference in Brussels. Strategically, one of the most important sessions was the policy one, held on 6 April with fostering open discussions and steps beyond SSHOC with the representatives of the EC, REA, ESFRI, and other four cluster projects (ENVRI-FAIR, EOSC-Life, ESCAPE and PANOSC), defining future coordination and upcoming opportunities for collaboration.

2.1.3 Other cross-cluster initiatives

Apart from the above-mentioned events and activities underlining cross-cluster collaboration aimed at aligning steps towards building EOSC, the clusters used a few more platforms for exchange:

- **ERIC Forum**²⁴: this initiative is aimed at advancing operations of ERICs and strategically contributing to the development of ERIC related policies. The ERIC Forum governance structure ensures proper representation from the five ESFRI clusters. For each cluster there is an executive board position. This stimulates the timely discussion of topics and issues of common concern that are related to the wider RI landscape, including EOSC.

²² Realising EOSC: Virtual Conference with a Difference news piece on SSHOC website: <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/news/realising-eosc-virtual-conference-difference> (accessed April 2022)

²³ Thematic Discovery Marketplaces for the European Open Science Cloud workshop page: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/events/realising-european-open-science-cloud/thematic-discovery-marketplaces-european-open-science-cloud> (accessed April 2022)

²⁴ ERIC Forum project website: <https://www.eric-forum.eu/> (accessed April 2022)

- **H2020 project ENRIITC²⁵**: this project aims to build a permanent pan-European network of Industrial Liaison and Contact Officers (ILOs and ICOs) and enable industry to become a full partner of research infrastructures whether it is as a user, a supplier, or a co-creator. CLARIN EIRC acted as the liaison between the SSHOC cluster and the other clusters
- **EOSC and ESFRI interest group²⁶**: created during July 2020, it aimed at sharing information among the ESFRI cluster projects and support a discussion regarding the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), supported by the representatives of the EOSC Secretariat project. The IG took on several relevant technical topics such as preventing re-invention, ensuring better understanding of existing platforms, developing use cases, finding niches in the clusters that currently go unnoticed, connecting technical developments in the clusters to EOSC, discussing interoperability and catalogues, providing feedback channel to the EOSC WGs on the utilization of the submitted deliverables, etc.

²⁵ ENRIITC project website: <https://enriitc.eu> (accessed April 2022)

²⁶EOSC and the ESFRIs Interest group page: <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/communities/EOSC-ESFRI> (accessed April 2022)

3. Challenges ahead

SSHOC is the first cluster project to be formally ending on 30 April 2022. The biggest challenge, not only for SSHOC, but for other clusters as well, is to keep their communities together as well as continue the fruitful collaboration between the clusters. SSHOC's tight-knit community already took steps towards the future together by committing via a Memorandum of Understanding to continue joint activities and collaborative projects, as well as to contribute to the maintenance and further dissemination and exploitation of project results. It is happening under the umbrella of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster initiative (keeping at the same time the same acronym SSHOC alive as established and recognisable brand).

For cross-clusters collaboration, all recommendations mentioned in the project brief remain relevant: building upon the unique position of the science clusters as a glue between the EOSC and research communities and end-users. Continued collaboration between the clusters remains a key precondition for enabling and supporting collaboration across disciplinary boundaries; it relies heavily on joint work by data science experts and infrastructural support that is informed by disciplinary dynamics, thus complementing the expertise on generic service provision and data handling practice. Finally, active support for the development of multidisciplinary research agendas requires innovative methodologies to handle very diverse types of datasets rooted in multiple domains.

SSHOC will continue its interdisciplinary workflow creation in the SSHOC Marketplace. The SSH Training Community sustainability scenarios include the potential integration under the Community of Practice (CoP) for training coordinators, but also the uptake from one of the ERICs.

Strategic coordination meetings between cluster communities will continue and initiatives for more formalised collaboration have been communicated to the EC and REA. A series of use cases was prepared, aiming at research agendas for the study a number of topics of interest and relevance for the upcoming funding period of HE and beyond.

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